

D6.3 - Model application in the two SCENT pilots using crowdsourced data coming from the SCENT platform

Smart Toolbox for Engaging Citizens into a People-Centric Observation Web

Abstract

Whilst citizen participation in environmental policy making is still in its infancy, there are signs of a growing level of interest. The majority of citizens, though, both as individuals and as groups often feel disengaged from influencing environmental policies. They also remain unaware of publicly available information, such as the GEOSS or Copernicus initiatives. The SCENT project will alleviate this barrier. It will enable citizens to become the ‘eyes’ of the policy makers by monitoring land-cover/use changes in their everyday activities. This is done through a constellation of smart collaborative technologies delivered by the SCENT toolbox in TRLs 6-8.

This deliverable describes the methodology of using the SCENT platform and the generated crowdsourced data in modelling. Comparative results of the models without and with crowdsourced data are provided, using pre-selected indicators. For selected areas covered with drone flights, results in terms of flood extent (Danube Delta), topography and land cover (Kifisos) were used for analysis and improvement of modelling results. Guidelines on future crowdsourcing research and practice are provided especially regarding different components of flood risk.

Keywords: hydrodynamic modelling, hydrological modelling, crowdsourced data, SCENT platform

D6.3

Dissemination Level: PU

Deliverable Type: R

Authoring and review process information	
EDITOR Thaine H. Assumpção / IHE Delft	DATE 05-08-2019
CONTRIBUTORS Thaine H. Assumpção / IHE Delft Ioana Popescu / IHE Delft Andreja Jonoski / IHE Delft Valantis Tsiakos / ICCS	DATE 15-08-2019 15-08-2019 15-08-2019 15-08-2019
REVIEWED BY Valantis Tsiakos / ICCS Iulian Nichersu / DDNI	DATE 11-12-2019 11-12-2019
APPROVED BY Athanasia Tsertou / ICCS Tony Hughes / CARR	DATE 13-12-2019 13-12-2019
LEGAL & ETHICAL ISSUES COMMITTEE REVIEW REQUIRED?	
NO	

Document/Revision history

Version	Date	Partner	Description
V0.1	15/08/2019	IHE Delft	First submission of Deliverable 6.3, for internal project review
V0.3	22/08/2019	CARR	Peer review report submitted
V0.6	26/08/2019	IHE Delft	Updated version submitted
V0.8	30/08/2019	DDNI	Peer review report submitted
V0.9	30/08/2019	IHE Delft	Revised, final version submitted
V1.0	30/08/2019	ICCS/CARR	Approved, final version submitted
V2.0	09/12/2019	IHE Delft	Revised to include use of drone data for modelling
V2.0	13/12/2019	ICCS/CARR	Approved, final version submitted

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
1D	One dimensional
2D	Two dimensional
CN	Curve Number
DD	Danube Delta
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
HEC	Hydrological Engineering Center
HEC-HMS	Hydrological Engineering Center – Hydrological Modelling System
HEC-RAS	Hydrological Engineering Center – River Analysis System
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
PoIs	Points of Interest
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
USACE	United States Army Corps of Engineers

Table 1: List of Abbreviations

Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.3 introduces the work carried out in Task 6.3, which aims at describing how the crowdsourced data collected through SCENT was used to improve hydrological and hydrodynamic model applications. This was carried out based on the initial models developed in Deliverable 6.1 and using the integration methods described in Deliverable 6.2. The applications are done for both SCENT pilot case studies, Danube Delta and Kifisos catchment.

The first part of the report, after the general introduction on the scope and intended readership, describes the methods used to retrieve the crowdsourced data from the SCENT platform and the steps taken in preparing this data for integration in the models. Through the SCENT Harmonisation platform and through the GEOSS platform, the data of interest for flood models can be obtained, which are the land cover maps, water depths and water velocities. For facilitating the access to the river data specifically, which is embedded in the images metadata, API's are also provided. The next step consisted in performing a data quality analysis of the images and videos obtained, to make sure they correspond to the model data needs. Through this process, all images and videos related to river parameters were individually visualized and assessed. For images the biggest issues found were lack of gauges, lack of water surface and low resolution. In terms of videos, issues such as freezing of the video frames and lack of the tracking object were the main diagnosed problems. After quality control the water depth and water velocities were extracted, taking into account other inaccuracies such as inaccurate location of the data. Lastly, it is presented the traditional river measurements carried out to compare with the crowdsourced data, as well as the steps taking in preparing them. For the Danube Delta it consisted of an acoustic profiler equipment, while for Kifisos catchment, varied methods were employed.

The second part of the report presents the steps taken into preparing the initial models for integration to crowdsourced data and the comparison of model results, crowdsourced data and traditional measuring methods, including the use of indicators. Due to the distinct characteristics of the case studies, the results are presented separately. In the case of the Danube Delta, it was realized that the crowdsourced water depths were very valuable and that the indicators computed using only traditional measurements and using crowdsourced data were comparable, indicating the usability of this data source. Velocity measurements were very variable in space and therefore did not perform as well in a close analysis. For Kifisos, more difficulties were found to obtain paired measurements but it was also visible that crowdsourced water levels matched well traditional measurements.

The third part covers the analysis of data generated from drone flights and how they were used in the two pilot areas. In Danube Delta (Sontea-Fortuna area) the focus was on using the orthophoto images for analysing flood extent as observed by the drones and simulated by the model. For the set of areas covered with drone flights visual comparison of modelled and observed flood extent was carried out, as well as using existing and newly proposed numerical indicators for assessing the quality of modelled flood extent. In the Kifisos pilot drone generated digital elevation and land-cover information was used to produce updated topography and roughness data used in the hydrodynamic model.

In a fourth part of the report, guidelines are presented to suggest the best practices in terms of using the results of these analyses and in terms of further research that can be conducted. The guidelines are separated data collection, data processing/analysis, data integration and data use, given the goal

of flood modelling. For practice, the most important point is that the process of data acquisition needs to be designed having into account reducing the data quality issues identified and that usage of crowdsourced water depths are preferred to validate flood models over the use of the velocity values. In terms of research, it lies indeed on how to better harness the information regarding velocity.

Lastly, the report ends with the conclusions, in which it is highlighted the overall tacit gain of implementing citizen science campaigns, as the flood models are frequently revisited and re-discussed with the community and ultimately, improving the local knowledge on floods.

1 Introduction

The simulation of rivers water flow and hydrological processes in catchments using computational models constitutes a valuable tool for decision-makers to assess the behaviour of the physical system under consideration. Moreover, when floods are the problem to be addressed, models can serve as a base for discussion and evaluation of possible adaptive measures to control their impact on the environment. In this context, the SCENT Toolbox includes models representing hydrology and/or hydrodynamics of flow, in relation to flood events.

These models, however, require large amounts of data to be properly parameterized and thus, to provide accurate results. This problem is magnified when there are frequent changes in the area, in the form of dredging or in the form of widespread change in land cover. Therefore, in SCENT a citizen-based approach to data collection was proposed and carried out. This was done in two case studies, in the Danube Delta, in Romania, and in Kifisos catchment in Greece. Hydrodynamic and hydrological models were already developed to characterize the area based on existing data.

Alternative sources of data involving citizens involve uncertainties that are unknown and are being investigated by the scientific community. This document contributes to this literature, in which it is discussed which are these uncertainties and how the final dataset improves modelling by providing more data than would normally be available.

1.1 Purpose of the Document

This report is the outcome of the work carried out in SCENT, Work Package 6 “Turning observations into spatiotemporal flooding patterns”. Work Package 6 objective is reached through three tasks:

- 6.1: Development of hydrodynamic and hydrological models of the Danube Delta and Kifisos pilot case studies using existing data sources
- 6.2.: Development of improved methods for modelling-oriented merging of crowdsourced data with existing data sources for better assessments of flood risks and spatiotemporal flooding patterns
- 6.3: Improved modelling of flooding patterns

The present report describes the work carried out in Task 6.3, which aims at improving existing models using crowdsourced data, with the aim of better characterizing flooding patterns.

1.2 Intended readership

Present report is intended to be used by parties (e.g. scientists and governmental authorities) with an interest of using crowdsourced data to improve their understanding of floods.

1.3 Relationship with other SCENT deliverables

The present deliverable is linked with Deliverable 7.1 on “SCENT enhanced datasets for images and text as web services”, in which it is discussed in more detail how the crowdsourced data is obtained through the SCENT platform. It is also related to Deliverables 7.2 and 7.3, on the field campaigns, where it is explained in more detail how the data used was collected. This deliverable is also source of information for Deliverable 7.4 on “Evaluation of the SCENT Toolbox”, as it indicates the results in terms of floods. Lastly, this deliverable is extremely linked with Deliverable 6.1, as it contains the results of

models without crowdsourced data, used for comparison in this deliverable. Deliverable 6.2 is also linked, as it defines the approaches and the indicators used for the comparative analysis.

1.4 Document Structure

The report is structured in 5 parts. After this introduction, a description of the methodology to integrate crowdsourced data is made in Section 2 of the report, where the acquisition of data from the SCENT platform and the methodologies to process and analyse the data are discussed. Section 3 describes the comparative analysis of the processed data. This analysis is split per case study, due to their differences. It is shown the data used to prepare the models for simulations of the campaign periods and the comparisons for water depth and velocity. Section 4 presents the analysis of drone data and how they were used in the two pilot areas. In Section 5 a reflection on the results obtained is provided together with guidelines for future research and practice. Lastly, the report ends with the conclusion section where the added value of crowdsourced data for modelling is discussed.

2 Methodology for crowdsourced data integration

In the Scent project, several types of data were collected by citizens, generating a large volume of information. This information has been handled and distributed through the Scent toolbox by the Scent Crowdsourcing Backend, processed by the Scent Intelligence Engine and standardized in the Scent Harmonization Platform. From all the data made available in the latter, the data relevant to hydrological/hydrodynamic model is the following:

- Water depths
- Water velocities
- Land cover/land use maps

In Deliverable 6.2, it was proposed methods to integrated river obstacle data (e.g. tree branches inside the canal). However, as after the campaigns it was not possible to collect such opportunistic data, these integration method is not used in this deliverable.

In the following sections, it is demonstrated how the data was retrieved from the Scent platform (Section 2.1), how it was further pre-processed for integration in the models (Section 2.2) and lastly, it is summarized from Deliverable 6.2 how the data was integrated into the models.

2.1 Retrieving crowdsourced data from SCENT platform

The various citizen-generated data, in-situ information and added-value products (i.e. land cover / land use maps) produced in the context of the project are managed, stored and provided by the Scent Harmonisation platform, while ensuring also their translation to standardised resources following the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards.

More specifically, the OGC SensorThings API¹ is utilised for the modelling of both crowdsourced and in-situ measurements collected in the context of Scent, establishing an interconnected and interoperable web of environmental observations. Thus, a dedicated API has been implemented supporting all the requests and filtering capabilities described in the standard. In order to perform CRUD actions (create, read, update, and delete functions) on the resources, the first step is to address to the target resources through Uniform Resource Identifiers (URI). The root URI of the service is <http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/>. Based on this and by defining the resource path and the query options, different actions can be performed on the available resources. Further details regarding the supported interfaces and requests are provided in deliverable D7.1.

In addition, users can access the Scent Harmonisation platform visualisation site², dedicated to visualizing and inspecting all citizen-generated and conventional in-situ data. The visualisation site provides also a catalogue, enabling users to find details regarding the different resources exposed by the platform and offered to GEOSS (Global Earth Observation System of Systems) portal. Regarding the latter, OGC Web Feature Services (WFS) and Web Mapping Services (WMS) services have been implemented, enabling the provision of metadata for the exposed resources and their presentation in a uniform manner as map overlays (See Deliverable D7.1).

¹ <https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/sensorthings>

² <http://scent-harm.iccs.gr/>

The metadata about the operations, services, and data (“capabilities”) that are offered by the Harmonisation platform WMS and WFS services are provided by the following service requests:

- <http://147.102.5.93:8080/geoserver/geomesa/wfs?service=WFS&version=1.1.0&request=GetCapabilities>
- <http://147.102.5.93:8080/geoserver/ows?service=WMS&version=1.1.0&request=GetCapabilities>

Additional information produced by the toolbox components such land cover/land use maps, water depth maps, water velocity maps and discharge time series, are also made available through WMS & WFS services.

More importantly, apart from the abovementioned means (OGC SensorThings API, WMS and WFS), the general public, including researchers outside the consortium and in the post-funding period, can also access SCENT resources directly via the GEOSS Portal catalogue (<https://www.geoportal.org/?f:sources=wfsscentID%2CwmsSCENTID>).

Last but not least, a custom API has been implemented, aiming to facilitate access to the crowdsourced data by the rest of the toolbox components such as the Scent Campaign Manager. A specific URI format is utilised, enabling relevant stakeholders to obtain the needed information. Data can be filtered in terms of date, location, pilot, tag and id, whilst receiving the information in JSON format.

The format is:

<base_uri>/<resource_requested>?<pilot>&<bb>&<time_range>&<id>&<property_name>&<tag>&<format>

The <base_uri> refers to the server where the information is stored, <http://147.102.5.93:8090/harmonisation/>. The <resource_requested> may be image, video, event report, sensor metadata, air temperature or soil moisture.

The filter parameters are optional, can be used simultaneously or independently and are:

- <pilot>: can be either kifisos or danube
- <bb>: should include the four corners of a rectangle
- <time_range>: one or two timestamps indicating the time span for the resources
- <id>: the feature id, in case all the information for only one id is needed
- <property_name>: returns only the specified properties for the features included in the result
- <tag>: this additional filter is available only for the images, and performs a keyword search in list containing all the validated tags referring to this image
- <format>: this filter indicates if the result should be a GeoJSON or a GML file.

Harnessing the API’s capabilities and in order to access crowdsourced data through the Scent Campaign Manager³, authorities follow these steps: select a pilot area; locate on the map a specific area of interest within the pilot area; select the campaign covering this area(Figure 1.a); select the closest Point of Interest (PoI) to the area they are interested in (Figure 1.b); and select the type of data

³ <https://scent.iccs.gr/>

(image, video or sensor data) that they want to access. The end result is a dashboard with images, video or sensor measurements, including the calculated water depths or velocities (Figure 1.c) spatially located within the radius of the PoI. This interface gives authorities a quick overview of the data collected through the campaigns.

For obtaining water level and water velocities, both raw images/videos and calculated values were retrieved. The retrieval was done through the customized API's, filtering by pilot and by date, using a Python script.

As an example, for obtaining the water velocities for all the Danube pilots the request was: <http://147.102.5.93:8090/harmonisation/video?pilot=danube>. Similarly, for obtaining all the images that had water level information from the first pilot held at Kifisos the request was: <http://147.102.5.93:8090/harmonisation/image?from=%272018-09-14%27&to=%272018-09-16%27&tag=%27Water%20Level%20Indicator%27>

The script resulted in a catalogue of “Water Level Indicator” images and videos and excel spreadsheets containing the relevant metadata.

Figure 1: Some of the steps to retrieve crowdsourced data through Scent Campaign manager. (a) Select campaign; (b) Select Point of Interest; (c) Visualize results for videos.

2.2 Data analysis and processing

Only data collected in the river campaigns need processing, the land cover maps are provided ready to use in the model (further parametrization is described in sections 3.1.1. and 3.1.2). In the Danube Delta, two campaigns were carried out, a dry campaign on Sep/2018 (#DD2) and a wet campaign in May/2019 (#DD3). In Kifisos catchment, the wet campaign took place in Nov/2018 and the dry one on Feb/2019. Due to the unpredictability of the Greek weather, river data was also collected in other campaigns and these data are included in the analysis.

The water-related crowdsourced data from SCENT forms a unique and novel dataset. Thus, in a first instance, a quality analysis of the data is performed, to understand the errors involved and which part of the dataset is suitable for extracting measurements (Section 2.2.1). The next step involves extraction of river measurements from crowdsourced data (Section 2.2.2) and, lastly, it is necessary to process the data from traditional measurements as well.

2.2.1 Image/videos quality analysis

To measure river characteristics generally implies to collect three data types: the measurement value (depth/velocity), the coordinates and the time stamp. Through the collection process, uncertainties can be associated with these data and the quality of overall dataset decreases if uncertainties are present. Therefore, it is important to identify and quantify such uncertainties.

In Scent, photos were taken of water gauges and videos recorded the movement of tennis balls to measure water depths and water velocities, respectively. As these are indirect measurements and the context of data collection is not traditional, uncertainties are present. These images/videos are accompanied by the smartphone's GPS coordinates. These can be uncertain due to the GPS accuracy, but also because the phone's coordinates do not correspond with the gauge/tennis ball location. Lastly, the smartphone's timestamp is also obtained and the uncertainties associated to it can be considered insignificant.

All images collected were analysed individually. The analysis was carried out in four parts, two on quality analysis and two on extraction of the water level and other relevant information:

1. Invalidation criteria [Yes/No]: criteria that if met automatically invalidates the image
 - 1.1. No visible gauge
 - 1.2. No water level
 - 1.3. Gauge is tilted (too much)
 - 1.4. Gauge has bad printing (too much)
 - 1.5. Gauge is far (too much)
 - 1.6. Image resolution is low (too much)
 - 1.7. Image has bad contrast (too much)
 - 1.8. Bad capturing angle – gauge is turned sideways (too much)
 - 1.9. Bad capturing angle – picture is taken from up looking down (too much)
 - 1.10. Image is unfocused (too much)
 - 1.11. Other
2. Quality criteria [0-3]: 0: Issue not detected; 1: a little; 2: moderate; 3: a lot
 - 2.1. Gauge is tilted
 - 2.2. Gauge has bad printing
 - 2.3. Gauge is far
 - 2.4. Image resolution is low
 - 2.5. Image has bad contrast
 - 2.6. Bad capturing angle – gauge is turned sideways
 - 2.7. Bad capturing angle – picture is taken from up looking down
 - 2.8. Image is unfocused
 - 2.9. There are waves in the water surface

- 2.10. Lack of bank reference
- 2.11. Other
- 3. Extraction:
 - 3.1. Water depth value in meters
 - 3.2. Uncertainty:
 - 1: certain of value
 - 2: in doubt between two values (+- 0.5 cm)
 - 3: in doubt among three values (+- 1 cm)
 - 5: in doubt among five values (+- 2 cm)
 - [range]: provides the range of possible values
 - 3.3. Extraction type
 - 0: reading from numbers and markings
 - 1: reading from bad markings
 - 2: inferring from the numbers and/or markings far from the water surface
- 4. Extra information: helpful data for comparison
 - 4.1. Gauge type (0: portable; 1: fixed)
 - 4.2. Cross-section positioning: location along the cross section
 - 4.2.1. c: close
 - 4.2.2. c-m: close-middle
 - 4.2.3. m: middle
 - 4.2.4. m-f: middle-far
 - 4.2.5. f: far

In the Danube Delta, after filtering for the pilot area and campaign period, a total of approximately 1200 images were tagged as 'Water Level Indicator', either by citizens or by the SCENT Intelligence Engine. In both campaigns, at least 70% of the images were valid, mostly due to the proximity of the volunteers to the gauge (Figure 2). It can also be seen that most of the valid images have high quality, fitting uncertainty levels 1 and 2 (up to 2 cm deviation). In the second campaign, the quality of the images lightly declined. By evaluating the causes (Figure 3), the main reason for invalidation was the lack of a gauge (i.e. random pictures), because the images tags were not validated as they need further annotation in SCENT Collaborate. Other than that, many images were taken of the gauge without including the water surface. Lastly, in campaign #DD3, about 8% of the invalidated images had the wrong geo-location; all had the same coordinates pointing to a non-visited location within the study area.

Figure 2: Proportions of validated and invalidated water level gauge images in the Danube Delta campaigns

Figure 3: Main causes for invalidation of images in the Danube Delta campaigns (image could meet more than one criteria)

In Kifisos, through 4 campaigns, 787 images were obtained. Percentages of valid images between 53-66% and the quality of the images decreased, resulting in more uncertainty of the extracted values (Figure 4).

Figure 4: (a) Number of images and (b) proportions of validated and invalidated water level gauge images in the Kifisos campaigns

At least half of the invalidated images were discarded due to incorrect tags (Figure 5), but it is visible that the more challenging and diverse environments of Kifisos influenced the results. As the citizens were collecting images from the river banks, sometimes the distance was too large for the image to be good, or the combination of average distance with a poor camera. In such cases it was not possible to visualize the water depth. Another factor was that the gauges painted in the river banks would have poor markings or damaged paint for the low water levels recordings, making it difficult to define the water depth. Specifically, for February campaign (#K3), 20% of all images were discarded (category other) because they were duplicates, probably the result of some technical problem.

Figure 5: Main causes for invalidation of images in the Kifisos campaigns (image could meet more than one criteria)

Similarly, videos were also analysed individually for their quality. The analysis was performed by IHE partners, including a TU Delft MSc intern. Four sets of criteria are defined:

1. Invalidation criteria [Yes/No]: criteria that if met automatically invalidates the video
 - 1.1. No ball
 - 1.2. More than one ball
 - 1.3. Full video disturbance
 - 1.3.1. Throwing
 - 1.3.2. Recovering
 - 1.3.3. Contact with bank
 - 1.3.4. Ball is stuck
 - 1.3.5. Ball thrower interferes
 - 1.3.6. Other
 - 1.4. Full video very bad quality
 - 1.4.1. Camera follows the ball (too much)
 - 1.4.2. Camera is shaking (too much)
 - 1.4.3. Video is freezing (too much)
 - 1.4.4. Bad recording angle (too much)
 - 1.4.5. Ball is hard to see (too much)
 - 1.4.6. Ball is far (too much)
 - 1.4.7. Bad path (too much)

- 1.4.8. Bad path – Waves (too much)
- 1.4.9. Valid video is too short (too much)
- 1.4.10. Other
- 2. Video cutting needed [Yes/No – specify cause]: Defines if the video can be used as a whole or if it needs cutting due to some disturbance or quality issue in the beginning or end of the video. Defines if the valid videos are fit for automatic extraction of velocity.
- 3. Quality criteria: [0-3]: should consider only the portion of the video that can be used to extract velocity. 0: Issue not detected; 1: a little; 2: moderate; 3: a lot
 - 3.1. Disturbances to ball movement (specify)
 - 3.2. Camera follows the ball
 - 3.3. Camera is shaking
 - 3.4. Video is freezing
 - 3.5. Bad recording angle
 - 3.6. Ball is hard to see
 - 3.7. Ball is far
 - 3.8. Bad path
 - 3.9. Bad path – Waves (too much)
 - 3.10. Valid video is too short (too much)
 - 3.11. Lack of video reference
 - 3.12. Other
- 4. Extra information: data that can be helpful in velocity extraction and/or uncertainty estimation
 - 4.1. Cross-section positioning: location along the cross section
 - 4.1.1. c: close
 - 4.1.2. c-m: close-middle
 - 4.1.3. m: middle
 - 4.1.4. m-f: middle-far
 - 4.1.5. f: far

Unfortunately, in the Danube Delta, difficulties were experienced during the execution of the first river data collection campaign and few videos were uploaded to the database (less than 100). Apart from these, additional videos collected without the app were also used. In the third Danube Delta campaign (#DD3), approximately 1200 videos were obtained. Four videos were invalidated in #DD2, mainly because the ball was too far, while for #DD3, approximately half were good for automatic extraction of velocity (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Proportions of validated and invalidated water velocity videos in the Danube Delta campaigns

The invalidation from #DD3 was done mostly on the grounds of video freezing, followed by being hard to see the ball due to colour similarity with the water – naturally or because of sun reflection (Figure 7). These problems are amplified in the Danube Delta, due to very low velocities.

Figure 7: Main causes for invalidation of videos in the Danube Delta campaigns (image could meet more than one criteria)

In Kifisos, the first two campaigns were very successful in terms of volume, with over 200 videos each (Figure 8). Due to weather conditions (either heavy rainfall or extreme sun), some campaign days were cancelled and/or attendance was reduced. Considering quality, around 75% of the videos are at least partially valid through all campaigns, with the performance mostly increasing as the campaigns proceed.

Figure 8: (a) Number of videos and (b) proportions of validated and invalidated videos in the Kifisos campaigns

It is visible that for Kifisos the main causes for invalidation were similar among campaigns, at different proportions (Figure 9). Videos without the ball were the main problem, trailed by quality problems related to the citizen moving the camera while recording, following the ball movement; and by video freezes. For the third campaign, another issue was that many videos were collected in an inappropriate location where the flow divides; data which can be used for testing extraction tool but for modelling it does not contribute.

Figure 9: Main causes for invalidation of videos in the Kifisos campaigns (image could meet more than one criteria)

Before velocity extraction, the videos pass through a data quality control mechanism embedded in the water velocity extraction tool. This process prevents, for example, that there are too few frames to perform the velocity calculation. From the 553 validated videos mentioned above, in #DD3, 239 were considered invalid for velocity extraction, about 43%. For Kifisos, a bit more, 57% of the videos were invalid for extraction in the first river campaign. For the other campaigns these proportions drop, for #K3, #K4 and #K5 around 35%, 13% and 25% of the videos were removed, respectively.

2.2.2 River measurements

In order to compare crowdsourced data with traditional measurements and model results, the first step is to extract the water depth and water velocity values. As mentioned in the previous section, water depths were read from all valid images, to obtain a dataset with high accuracy. Velocity values

were calculated by the water velocity extraction tool, for which more information can be found in Deliverable 5.2. The exception are the videos from #DD2, these were processed manually using the procedure described in Annex A, since a portion of the videos was not collected through the app.

Moreover, extra steps need to be taken to obtain a final, consistent dataset that is locally relevant, i.e. represents the reality of the Point of Interest (PoI) investigated. Thus, for the images and videos validated in the quality analysis, these steps are, per campaign and per PoI:

- Control location accuracy: reject measurement more than 30m away from another one;
- Control time accuracy: reject measurement more than 20 min apart from another one;
- Cluster data per location in the river, i.e. left bank or right bank (where possible);
- Per cluster, control value accuracy (i.e. exclude extreme outliers); and
- Per cluster, calculate average.

Through this process, in #DD3, 8% of the images had inaccurate locations and 11% were taken in locations where no traditional measurement was carried out. Inaccuracies due to time and value were insignificant. The final distribution of images is displayed in Figure 10. For videos, inaccuracies related to location time and value amounted to 5%, 1% and 7% respectively, with 8% of the data not paired with traditional measurement data.

In the case of Kifisos, inaccuracies were insignificant, as in all campaigns only one or two images would be inaccurate in space. Only one video had wrong positioning. The exception was the first campaign, in which 9 images were badly positioned, still corresponding to a low percentage of 5%. The match with traditional measurements is analysed in Section 3.2.2.

Figure 10: In Danube Delta, locations of valid images, images with inaccuracies and images not paired with ADCP data

2.2.3 Traditional river measurements

Traditional river measurements consist of measuring water depths and water velocities through consolidated methods described in the scientific literature. They serve three purposes: evaluate the quality of the crowdsourced data collected, evaluate the quality of model simulations and be a benchmark for defining if models are improved by using crowdsourced data.

Five different types of traditional measurements were used:

- Danube Delta:
 - Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP): water depth and velocity
- Kifisos catchment:
 - Water level telemetric gauges: water depth and velocity (discussed in Deliverable 3.1)
 - Float method: water depth and velocity
 - Flow meter: water depth and velocity
 - Radar velocimetry: velocity

In Kifisos, a radar velocimetry equipment had been obtained to be installed together with the telemetric water gauge. However, due to the high risk of theft, the equipment was used portably in alternation with the other described methods, based on the availability of equipment.

ADCP data

The Danube Delta is a remote natural area with deep, wide channels. In such cases, measurements need to be made with a mobile equipment, as it is not possible to leave it in the field, and with an equipment that can handle large scales. Thus, measurements are made with an Acoustic Doppler Profiler, more specifically, an M9 ADP, which can be used for shallow and deep channels. The measurements are performed by emitting beams into the water and capturing the reflection from particles within the water and from the bottom (Figure 11a). Data is collected by navigating with the equipment across the river of the desired location. The end result is a velocity and depth profile from each surveyed cross section (Figure 13b).

Figure 11: (a) M9 ADP characteristics. Source: Sontek (2016); (b) Example of ADCP profile.

SonTek RiverSurveyor software was used to visualize, read and process the ADCP measurements. Different configurations are available within the tool, including the tracking method and the depth reference. As the velocity of the velocity measured by the instrument is a combination of water and boat velocity, the Bottom-Track reference velocity was selected, which calculates boat velocity relative to the stationary riverbed, and this information is used to estimate the water velocity. Vertical Beam was the chosen depth reference, in which the water depth is determined by highly accurate echo sounder.

During field measurements, it is a normal practice to have many tracks of ADCP measurements at one location, to have a choice for selection of good quality data. Therefore, the quality of each

measurement was analysed and the outliers were removed. The selection was carried out in two main stages, as per the guidelines provided in the equipment’s user manual. These included:

- Evaluate the validity of bottom track, GPS, vector track GPS (velocity) and depth reference were inspected.
- Evaluate the tracks (path taken during measurement). It was selected tracks with the minimum difference between the angle of average GPS course and ADP bottom-track course; and smooth tracks (i.e. horizontal), with mostly uniform velocity lines perpendicular to tracks (Figure 12a).

Tracks with regions of invalid bottom-track data (Figure 12b) were also discarded, as well as records where the trajectory of the measurement was incomplete. For samples in the same location, the channel width, wetted area and duration of measurements should be similar.

Figure 12: (a) Example of GPS and bottom-track tracks; (b) Example of profile data with a region of invalid bottom-track

In the #DD2 campaign, 35 valid tracks were obtained, while in the #DD3 campaign, 203 were obtained, out of with 58 were valid.

Float method and flow meter

The float method is one of the simplest methods to estimate river discharge and it is the method that inspired the velocity measurements of SCENT. It consists of (Figure 13):

- Selecting suitable river reach for measurement (straight channel with smooth bottom and non-turbulent flow).
- Set 2 sets of measuring tape perpendicular to the flow direction, starting in the dry terrain and ending in dry terrain
- Calculate the distance between measuring tapes
- Define the spacing of the transects in which the measurements will be performed
- At each transect, measure the water depth
- At each transect, release a floatable object
- Time how long it takes for the floatable object to reach the downstream tape set
- Repeat three times per transect and average the results
- Repeat for all transects

Figure 13: (a) Schematization of the float method. Source: after Fig. 3.17, Sanders (1998); (b) Flow meter

The flow meter is a simple equipment composed of a rod with a propeller in one of its ends and a digital marker at the other end, informing the velocity and other additional information. In order to use it, the process is similar to the float method. The differences are that only one tape needs to be fixed and that instead of introducing the floatable object in the water the propeller is inserted and one minute is necessary to pass by for each reading. The reading can be done at a fixed water depth or averaged through depth, by moving the gauge up and down. It is considered more accurate to use the averaged version, so that is the one used. In some cases however, the water depth was so low that there was no room for moving the meter.

The results of each measurements are the full velocity and depth profile of the section (Figure 14). Due to time constraints during the campaigns, in some cases only the depth profile would be obtained. The float method was used in #K2 and #K5, while the flow meter was used in #K3.

Figure 14: Water level profile obtained with the float method at Monastiri station in Kifisos, during #K5 campaign

Radar velocimetry

The radar velocimetry equipment allows for capturing of the water surface velocity. It emits waves towards the water and calculates the velocity based on the varied pattern of reflections emitted back due to water movement. Therefore, this method cannot be used in small streams where interferences with the river bank cannot be isolated and where the water is almost still. It also does not capture velocities lower than 0.1 m/s.

The radar was placed in the centre of each cross-section surveyed and data was collected for an approximate time of 3 minutes, given that the velocity values converged (Figure 15a). Consequently, one value of velocity is collected per location. The quality of the measurement was also in-situ by checking the histogram of emitted values (Figure 15b).

Figure 15: (a) Example of radar velocimetry survey; (b) Example of the interface where measurements are done

3 Comparative analysis

After the datasets have been properly processed, analysed and filtered based on their quality, they are prepared to be either used in the model or be used for model validation. These results are separated by case study once the modelling strategy is distinct for each of them. First it is presented the preparation done to run the models for the campaign periods, without and with crowdsourced data. Further on, it is shown the validation in terms of water depth and water velocity. It is then assessed how well the crowdsourced data is and it is done a comparative analysis of the ability of the model to be validated without and with crowdsourced data, using the proposed indicators. The comparative analysis was viable only where all the datasets were available.

3.1 Sontea-Fortuna

The Sontea-Fortuna case study is modelled by a HEC-RAS 1D/2D hydrodynamic model, built, calibrated and validated with existing data. As mentioned in Section 2, two river campaigns were carried out for this area and thus, results are shown in terms of these campaigns.

3.1.1 Model preparation

For each campaign, the first essential data necessary is the upstream boundary condition, a hydrograph, containing the discharges for the campaign period. This should include with 5 days before and 5 days after of data. The dry (#DD2) and wet campaign (#DD3) of Danube Delta had different discharge values, however, for the wet campaign discharges represented average flow conditions (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Upstream boundary condition hydrograph for (a) #DD2 campaign and (b) #DD3 campaign

In SCENT, a citizens also crowdsourced images of land cover and through the map segmentation tool, an updated land cover map was obtained. This land cover map was associated with roughness coefficients for each of the land covers detected by the map segmentation tool (Figure 17). Although not many classes are used, the map provides a highly spatial variability of roughness coefficients.

Figure 17: Map of Manning roughness coefficients used in the Danube Delta based on the updated land cover map.

3.1.2 Water depth

For the Danube Delta, 32 locations were available for the #DD2 campaign, while 52 were available for #DD3. From the first campaign, it was possible to find very good results (i.e. the three data sources are similar), average results (water depth values are somewhat similar) and bad results (values are not close). In Figure 18, in the top panel, it can be seen that the model provides good results compared to the traditional data and that the crowdsourced data also indicates that the model is good. For the average comparison, it can be seen that the model is performing on average compared to ADCP and that, although crowdsourced data is overestimating depths compared to ADCP, it also gives the model an average performance. However, if analysing the spread of points, this is a very sensitive analysis: if crowdsourced data were not collected on both sides of the cross section, the validation would be biased. Lastly, in the bottom panel, the model is clearly biased and that is due to the wrong location of the river terrain, as can be seen in the left side. Despite the model's inaccuracy, the crowdsourced data was able to diagnose such problem.

Figure 18: Comparative analysis of crowdsourced water depth, ADCP measurements and model results (a) a good comparison; (b) an average comparison; and (c) a bad comparison. Adapted from Mathre (2019).

By pairing all the data for analysis (using all the data and not only the places where the three are available, due to the scarcity), the crowdsourced data is mostly close to ADCP data (Figure 19). The ADCP data scores the model as bad (most probably because of the terrain), while the crowdsourced data validate the model as equally good and bad.

Figure 19: Number of good, average and bad comparisons for different sources of data

3.1.3 Water velocity

Due to the lack of videos, only 9 comparisons were possible for #DD2. For #DD3, results were obtained in 52 locations. Results for velocity were much harder to analyse, because in the Danube Delta velocities are very low and even traditional equipment has oscillations, as can be seen in Figure 20. Moreover, model results are given as average velocity, so although for one video the comparison was good, most of them the comparison was bad because model velocities were close to zero.

Figure 20: Good average and bad comparisons of velocity data in the Danube Delta. Adapted from Mathre (2019).

3.1.4 Indicators

The graphical comparison per POI of water depths and velocities are valuable to diagnose problems of the model and to understand what the factors that make crowdsourced data usable for model improvement are. However, it is also necessary to calculate some quantitative metrics on how the model is performing. The metrics calculated are the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), as described in Deliverable 6.2.

For #DD2, it can be seen that both ADCP and crowdsourced data agree with an MAE error in the order of 80-90 cm, for water depths (Figure 21). From the spread in the graph, it is visible that the problem is with smaller channels. For velocities, although the individual comparisons were not very similar, the overall metrics are (Figure 22). These metrics indicate that the model representation is not good, with around 100% standard deviation, as a flow of 0.1 m/s is common in this case study. For #DD3, similar results were found for #DD3.

Figure 21: MAE and RMSE for water depths; and velocities in the Danube Delta. Source: Mathre (2019).

Figure 22: MAE and RMSE for velocities in the Danube Delta. Source: Mathre (2019).

3.2 Kifisos catchment

The Kifisos catchment is composed of one event-based HEC-HMS hydrological model coupled with a hydrodynamic 2D HEC-RAS hydrodynamic model. These models have been calibrated and validated with data from 2000 and 2001, due to the fierce scarcity of flow data in Kifisos catchment. Results were analysed according to the crowdsourced data collected from four river campaigns, as mentioned in Section 2.

3.2.1 Model preparation

For the Kifisos catchment, the main information necessary for running the models is precipitation data. Rainfall data was obtained for the four campaigns. For the first river campaign (#K2), the rainfall event prior to the campaign (approximately 5.8mm) was not significant to generate runoff results for the hydrological model. Likewise, for campaign #K4 the previous rainfall event was too earlier than the campaign. For the last campaign (#K5), no rainfall occurred. For the second campaigns with river data collection (#K3), daily rainfall was obtained from 7 meteorological stations, interpolated to smaller intervals and interpolated in space using the inverse distance weighting method (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Example of rainfall data used to run Kifisos hydrological model. This is the rainfall at Tatoi station for the third kifisos campaign (#K3)

For Kifisos catchment, the land cover map produced by the map segmentation tool, based on images taken by citizens, was used to define soil properties, related to the soil perviousness. This is implemented through the Curve Number parameter (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Curve Number values of the updated hydrological model with SCENT land cover map information. Value calculated based on detailed land cover map (left) and averaged values per sub-basin (right)

Lastly, drone data was used to update the digital elevation model and the roughness information of Kifisos hydrodynamic model (see Section 4.2).

3.2.2 Water depth & Velocity

Crowdsourced water depth and velocity data, in Kifisos catchment, can be directly used for comparisons with the hydrodynamic results. However, for the hydrological model, discharges are necessary, combining these data. Therefore, these data types are analysed together.

In Kifisos, 19 different locations were visited during the 4 campaigns in which river data was collected (Figure 25). In some of these locations more than one Pol was visited, with a total of around 25 Pols. From these, 11 are located in the most downstream portion of the catchment.

Figure 25: Visited locations during the Kifisos campaigns and locations where traditional measurements were carried out.

Table 2 summarizes which POIs were visited by volunteers in which campaign and from the locations visited in which of them paired traditional data collection was performed. As it can be seen, comparison can be made in 4, 5, 6 and 3 locations per campaign. Moreover, comparisons involving both water level and discharge in two to three points per campaign. Many aspects contributed to the lack of paired data in Kifisos: need of immediate comparison, because hydrological conditions change very quickly; variability of river conditions and of equipment; limited amount of personnel given the high number of volunteers that needed guidance; and traffic conditions and distant locations, reducing accessibility.

Table 2: Availability of paired crowdsourced and traditional data

Location	#Pol	#K2		#K3		#K4		#K5	
		Crowd*	Trad*	Crowd*	Trad*	Crowd*	Trad*	Crowd*	Trad*
1	1					D			
	2					D			
2	3			D & V					
	4			D & V					
	5			D & V	D & V				
3	6			D					
4	7			D & V					
	8			D & V					
5	9	V				D & V	D&V	D & V	D&V
6	10	D	D	D & V	D & V			D & V	
	11			V	V				
7 - T**	12	D & V	D	D & V	D	D & V	D&V	D & V	D&V
8	13	D & V	D & V			D & V	V	D & V	
	14	D & V				D & V	V	V	
	15	D & V	D & V			D		V	
9 - T**	16	D & V	D	D & V	D & V	D & V	D&V	D&V	D&V
10	17	D & V				D			
11	18	D & V							
12	19	D & V				D			
13	20	D				D			
14	21	D & V							
15	22	D							
16	23	D & V							
17	24	D & V							
18	25	D & V							
19	26	D & V				D	V		

On 17/02/2019, a paired analysis of water depths and velocities was carried out in Kokinos Milos station (#Pol 16), as displayed in Figure 26. Data on water depths was collected with the telemetric sensor and through field survey, while data on velocity was obtained with a flow meter. Using this data, the discharge measured from the river survey is 1 m³/s.

The crowdsourced data collected in the location had good temporal and spatial distribution, without outliers. For water depths, 34 readings were obtained, some from the stencil in the river bank and some from a portable gauge within the river. For velocities, 20 data points were obtained. From looking at the distribution of data values (Figure 27) and at the pictures taken, the difference in the water depths is due to the eroded bottom of the river, allowing water to accumulate at depths below the start of the painted stencil gauge (Figure 28). For velocity, values were more concentrated along the 0.1-0.15 m/s values.

Figure 26: Water levels and velocities collected with traditional methods. With gauging the cross-section for water level and velocity with a flow meter (top); and using the telemetric sensor (bottom)

Figure 27: Histograms of the water depths and velocities resultant from citizen data collection for Kokinos Milos station at the third Kifisos campaign (#K3)

Figure 28: Example of image taken from a citizen, showing that the water levels were very low, indicating almost zero velocity in the stencil gauge, but due to the eroded bed of the river there is depth in the middle of the channel.

The model provides the results in terms of discharge, at the end of each sub-basin, including the one that has as outlet the Kokinos Milos station (Figure 29). It is visible that the model is behaving well in terms of simulating the events quickly. From the rainfall event about 10 days before the campaign, a discharge of $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ is reached after the wave has passed.

Figure 29: Discharge time series result from the hydrological model for the third Kifisos campaign (#K3). (left) Whole simulation and (right) comparison period

Comparing the results (Table 3), it is visible that the water levels taken with the portable gauge were very close to the obtained with traditional measurements. The velocities were much lower than expected. If using the water levels and velocities, the discharge estimation for comparison with the model is also inaccurate in comparison with the field survey. However, if only the water depth is used a comparable result is reached. The model, did not represent well the low flows.

Table 3: Comparative analysis of traditional, crowdsourced and model results for Kifisos catchment at Pol 16

	Water depth [m]	Velocity [m/s]	Discharge [m ³ /s]
Traditional (telemetric)	0.21	NA	NA
Traditional (field survey)	0.24 (average)	0.93	1.0
Crowdsourced	0.07 (first cluster, stencil) 0.14 (second cluster) 0.19 (third cluster)	0.05	0.05 (estimated*) 1.5 (estimated**)
Model	NA	NA	8.8

* Using the surveyed cross-section; **Using only the water depths and Manning equation

On a similar method, on 16/07/2019, at the Pol #10 field survey was carried out (Figure 30). This is a larger cross-section, spanning 9.7 m. By looking at the comparisons (Table 4), the crowdsourced water levels have clusters because the portable gauge was positioned in different locations of the river, not necessarily at the survey location. The three clusters have very good values, very close to the traditional survey. In terms of velocities, this river has a more varied velocity profile, from 0.14 to 0.83 m/s. Therefore, although there are discrepancies in the average values, the results are within the surveyed range. The same is visible for the discharge, with both the traditional measurement and the crowdsourced data indicating that the model is overestimating the discharge considerably. Given the rapid response of the catchment, the reason for this behaviour may lay in the interpolation of the rainfall; daily rainfall data was obtained which is spread through the day in the interpolation process. It may be a misrepresentation of events that occurred more intensely during a few hours of the day.

Figure 30: Water levels and velocities collected with traditional methods. With gauging the cross-section for water level and velocity with a flow meter

Table 4: Comparative analysis of traditional, crowdsourced and model results for Kifisos catchment at Pol 10

	Water depth [m]	Velocity [m/s]	Discharge [m³/s]
Traditional (field survey)	0.29 (average)	0.44	1.4
Crowdsourced	0.40 (first cluster) 0.28 (second cluster) 0.34 (third cluster)	0.59	1.68 (estimated*)
Model	NA	NA	16.6

*estimated for second cluster

3.2.4 Indicators

In Kifisos catchment, due to circumstances described previously, there were few points in which it was possible to obtain paired traditional and crowdsourced data, as well as a considerable rainfall event to trigger the hydrological model. Therefore, it was not possible to compute indicators of performance as more data is needed to obtain reliable results.

4. Use of drone data for modelling

Drone data have been increasingly used by both the scientific community and authorities in the field of water resources management. In the context of SCENT, it was proposed that both crowdsourced data and drones are used to complement traditional monitoring efforts in support of flood modelling. The following sections describe how this was done for each case study.

4.1. Sontea-Fortuna

The Sontea-Fortuna case study is a complex wetland system, covering an extensive area of 350 km². In such regions, there are several hydraulic uncertainties that can be solved with drones, such as topography, land cover, flood extent and connectivity. As reported in deliverable D3.1 (see Figure 13 in that deliverable), Sontea-Fortuna is too large and drone surveys were limited to 10 areas, with main focus on analysis of flood extent. The executed drone flight areas are presented in Figure 31 (also shown in deliverable D7.2). The processed orthophotos from these areas were used for analysis.

Figure 31. Executed drone flight areas in the Sontea-Fortuna pilot

The flood extent comparative analysis was performed through the following steps:

- Step 1: flood extent extraction from drone orthophotos
- Step 2: flood extent extraction from hydrodynamic models
- Step 3: metrics calculation
- Step 4: result analysis

In step 1, the extraction was done by manually defining the boundary of the flood extent (Figure 32). It also included defining the boundary of the drone image (hereby denominated 'domain'). In step 2, a simulated flood extent was extracted for the domain of each drone orthophoto. The flood extent map used was obtained from the dry period simulation (Section 3.1.1.). Considering that the drone campaigns occurred from 12/10/2018 to 27/11/2018, the last simulated flood extent from 05/10/2018 was selected.

Figure 32. Example of step 1 (left) and Step 2 (right) of the flood extent comparative analysis. The yellow, blue and red lines represent, respectively, the orthophoto domain, the drone flood extent and the simulated flood extent.

The third step involves the calculation of metrics used to evaluate the model ability to simulate flood extent (Figure 33). In deliverable D6.2, the metrics used traditionally in the field of hydrodynamic modelling were presented, which are mostly based on a ratio of areas. It was discussed that such metrics didn't take into account the exact shape of the flood extent and thus, to evaluate that, experiments were performed in a benchmark case study using metrics originating from the fields of topology and pattern recognition. It was found that these metrics showed higher potential at identifying shapes. Accordingly, the result using the traditional metrics and the most promising topology metrics identified are presented, i.e. the Hausdorff Distance and the Modified Hausdorff distance.

Figure 33. Drone observed versus simulated flood extent in terms of areas (left) and in terms of shape (right)

Lastly, the results for all surveyed areas are analysed (Figure 34). Area 12 is not presented due to uncertainties in building the mesh (orthophoto) based on the individual photos taken by the drone.

Figure 34. All drone-surveyed orthophotos overlapped with drone (blue) and simulated (red) flood extents.

Regarding results presented in Figure 34, it should be noted that the resulting orthophoto was not accurate enough for flood extent extraction in certain locations, due to some shift in the original drone photos. In most cases these problems were not significant, however for areas 04 and 05 a large part of the image had to be disregarded.

Overall, it is clear that, as these images were collected in a dry period, the inundation extent was quite limited and corresponded to small fractions of the overall area. Furthermore, water was encountered mostly within the canals, except for area 07. The simulated flood extent, in contrast, was more extensive, spreading over the floodplain.

In terms of shapes, it can be seen that when not extremely over-predicting the flood extent (as for areas 01 and part of area 02, for example), the observed and simulated flood extent shapes are similar, mainly for areas 04, 05 and 07.

For the traditional metrics (Figure 35), the bias indicates over-prediction of areas 01 and 02 and 09, being also penalized in the F4 metric, which is designed for that purpose. The false alarm rate (F) has the same purpose but there these differences are not that marked, mainly because it also takes into account the correctly predicted dry areas. The F3 metric, which penalizes under-prediction, points towards area 04. However, its value is not high, as it would be expected as we can see very little under-prediction in the images. This is a better indicator for this purpose (penalizing under-prediction) than the hit rate, which is giving high success to most areas but 02. PC and CSI take both over and under prediction into account and it is visible that their values are more consistent with what can be seen in the images (an average performance overall). CSI is more drastic in penalizing over-prediction.

Figure 35. Traditional flood extent metrics computed for the comparative analysis (metrics are discussed in deliverable 6.2, Table 6)

For the metrics adopted from the field of topology, the main drawback is that they compute distances, which are not in a goodness-of fit scale (e.g. from good to bad). In these metrics, the higher distance indicates shapes that are further apart. By comparing these metrics among the surveyed areas (Figure 36), it is clear that areas 07 and 06 are considered significantly better than the rest. This may due to the fact that the extent predicted by the model in these shapes is closer to the observed extent. In the

other areas, the simulated extent is larger, with more rounded shapes, while the observed ones are straighter, thinner shapes. Thus, their shape points are further from the observed ones more frequently and they are penalized.

Figure 36. Topology metrics used for the flood extent comparative analysis (metrics are discussed in deliverable 6.2)

The Hausdorff distance and Modified Hausdorff Distance have thus, pointed to a different evaluation of the results. While PC and CSI highly disagree on the performance of areas 01 and 02, they both consider that better results were achieved in areas 04 and 07. Area 07 is also considered a better simulated according to the topology metrics.

These are novel applications of metrics that already offer insight on the distribution of floods in space. The power and applicability of these metrics needs to be further investigated for validation of the flood models, in terms of adapting it to operate within a scale that can be more easily interpreted and/or to study further the results' relationship with flood characteristics.

4.2 Kifisos catchment

Kifisos case study, in contrast to the Danube Delta, is a small, urban catchment in which drone flights could cover larger areas. As reported in deliverables D3.1 and D7.3, drone imagery was processed to obtain a Digital Surface Model (DSM), including building heights, and a Digital Terrain Model (DTM), without such over the ground features (Figure 37). Moreover, the orthophotos were used to obtain a land cover map (Figure 38) that was combined with the elevation information to derive the roughness coefficients.

Figure 37: The drone-based terrain outputs for Kifissos Catchment: DSM (left) and DTM (right). Source: Phuoc (2019)

Figure 38: Drone-based orthophotos (left) and LC map (right) of Kifissos catchment. Source: Phuoc (2019).

The effect of the topography was evaluated in the hydrodynamic model results by building three models: based on the original DEM available before the project, based on the drone DTM and on the drone DSM. As illustrated in Figure 39, it is clear the differences in detail, mainly when using the DSM that considers the buildings. Results showed that the drone surveys captured the different heights in river bank on the downstream, allowing the model to better simulate flooded conditions on the side that is lower. Moreover, the use of DSM worked better as the barrier to the flow imposed by buildings,

which in the DTM model was introduced via high roughness coefficients. Therefore, the DSM model was used for simulations with crowdsourced data.

More details about the drone processing and on modelling approaches can be found in Phuoc (2019).

Figure 39. Depths and inundation extent at the downstream of three models produced, using the original DEM (left), drone DTM (middle) and drone DSM (right). Source: Phuoc (2019)

5 Guidelines

The generation of rich datasets of crowdsourced data allowed the investigation of their usability for flood modelling, one of the contexts in which this alternative data collection approach was proposed. More than that, the process taken from each collected sample to the final model result allowed the consortium to learn about the best practices for navigating this road and made it clear that there is much research to be done to unveil the potential of crowdsourced data. The following sections discuss these topics, based on guidelines for data collection, data processing/analysis, data integration and data use, given the goal of flood modelling.

5.1 Future practice

Suggestions for future practice are described below. Most concern water levels and velocities, when related to land cover it will be explicitly said so.

- Data collection
 - The quality and validity of the collected images/videos were sometimes dictated by the environment (e.g. image has bad contrast), but sometimes by human error (e.g. no gauge or video including ball recovery). Thus, it is recommended that volunteers are provided with longer, more practical training sessions, as well as to receive more guidance in the field, in order to reduce the amount of invalid data
 - The quality of the crowdsourced measurements was affected by the characteristics of Points of Interest, mainly the ones in small channels. Even though a pre-survey of the area was carried out, including taking into account aspects such as channels smoothness (more information on Deliverable 7.2 and 7.3), it is recommended a more judicious approach to PoI selection. It is recommended that all proposed Pols are surveyed for their cross-sections, that the flow characteristics are investigated and that markings or documentation of exact good locations for the measurements are carried out.
 - Alternative solutions for water levels obtained from gauges painted in the river bank so as to enhance the resolution of the data.
- Data processing/analysis
 - The quality analysis performed was pivotal to understanding the dataset and spotting weaknesses that would result in bad results in terms of models. Even though extremely time consuming, while crowdsourcing is a new science, it is recommended to visually perform quality analysis of the dataset before using it.
- Data integration
 - The model results showed that water depth obtained from crowdsourced data can be used to validate flood models, as similar indicators were obtained with and without it. Locally, better results were obtained at Pols with more crowdsourced data. Therefore, it is recommended to do validation with data from locations with cluster of points, instead of single data points.
 - The model results showed that velocity measurements can provide an indication on the validity of models but they still contain a lot of variability, inherent from their variable nature. In view of that, it is recommended that when crowdsourced velocities

are used for model validation, that this is done in association with water depth crowdsourced data.

- Model results use
 - The chain from obtaining the data to achieving model validation provides good results; yet it might be time-consuming and requiring expertise. Such models improved with crowdsourced data in a campaign-based data collection are not recommended to be used for time-sensitive issues (i.e. during emergency situations).
 - In urban areas where there is danger in data collection, volunteers will not be able to collect data during high flows. Hence, crowdsourcing data should be associated with in-situ telemetric data in such cases, so as to allow for model uses involving flooding scenarios.

5.2 Future research

Suggestions for future research are described below. Most concern water levels and velocities, when related to land cover it will be explicitly said so.

- Data collection
 - Uncertainties in location affect velocity measurements more, mainly in wide channels and when the ball throw is done far from the recording location. Also, the amount of reference background in the video influences the quality of the extraction. Therefore, it is suggested that the gyroscope information from smartphones is investigated as an auxiliary dataset to improve the extraction.
- Data processing/analysis
 - Calibration and validation of hydrodynamic models is still done on the basis of accurate datasets and therefore, more research is needed in terms of improving the extraction of water level measurements at the centimetre scale.
 - Videos that include disturbances to the ball movement, such as reeling the ball back, affect a lot the calculation and therefore were left out of the analysis. Further research is suggested to investigate how to cut the video automatically, discarding the bad parts.
- Data integration
 - Model validation was performed regardless of the uncertainty of the measurements, however, these influence considerably the results. More research is needed on how to take into account this uncertainty, maybe through a weighted average, or if uncertain data can be discarded altogether.
 - On the same line, the work of SCENT showed that it is possible for citizens to collect both highly accurate water depths but also very varied velocities. However, when integration takes place, it is generally done only for single values. This work already mixed water depth and velocity data which is generally done separately, but research needs to go further into exploring validation by ranges.

- The variability of velocities measurements invokes the research on how to improve SCENT data collection in a way that discharge values can be calculated solely based on crowdsourced data.
- Model results use
 - Citizen science has been very successful in the field of water quality and the results obtained indicate that crowdsourced data can be explored for the validation of models. Thus, research on coupling hydrodynamic and water quality models and validating them using crowdsourced data could lead to models with a broader use.

6 Conclusions

In this document, it was discussed how images and videos collected through citizens campaigns result in improvement of flood models.

In SCENT, campaigns were organized in the Danube Delta and Kifisos catchment to collect land cover, water depth and velocity data, in the format of images (pictures of gauges and the landscape) and videos (taken all in movement). The quality of the dataset was analysed and, based on this analysis, a significant part of the dataset was invalidated, mainly due to incorrect tagging. The images provided a good source of very accurate data given that the image was taken close to the gauge, which was the case for the Danube Delta. For Kifisos, higher uncertainties were encountered due to the distance, thus resulting in images with lower resolution. Even though there were uncertainties in the location due to GPS inaccuracy, clustering the data proved a good alternative. Traditional datasets, such as ADCP measurements, were also processed.

The campaign periods were simulated with crowdsourced data (from the map segmentation tool). The validation was done without crowdsourced data (traditional measurements) and with crowdsourced data. For the Danube Delta, it was realized that crowdsourced water depths are a good source for validation. For Kifisos, the high uncertainty of the crowdsourced data and the unavailability of rainfall events close to the campaign periods caused very few results to be used, with considerable uncertainty as underground processes were not considered. It is expected that with more data on about the groundwater a continuous distributed model will perform better, as well as the collection of data with less uncertainty.

Overall, the whole process yielded positive results, mainly in the case of the Danube Delta where a large amount of high-quality crowdsourced water depths were obtained. One important tacit benefit from this campaign-based citizen science approach was the iterative look at the models and at the data. Several improvements were performed in the model due to the cyclic effort of looking designing campaigns and analysing data. A higher understanding of the system was achieved as well. Rigid quality control mechanisms are necessary so as to tackle the uncertainty of crowdsourced data and further facilitate their deployment in the context of the models.

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Appendices

A 1: Manual extraction of velocity from videos

The videos of the first river campaign of Danube Delta were analysed using the Tracker software, where each video is manually inserted, parameterized and processed to obtain the water velocity. The following description of the procedure was extracted from Mathre (2019), a study in which in-depth analysis of #DD2 crowdsourced data was carried out.

The Tracker video analysis and modelling traces the paths of objects through series of frames in reference to an axis and provides values such as distances in x and y directions, average velocity, x and y-component velocities with respect to time. The tool offers many other data, however these were the required data for the present research. The steps used to derive the required data from the crowdsourced videos through the Tracker tool is provided in the figure below.

The video was first imported in the software’s user interface. The tool imports videos as a series of image frames, with each frame of a defined time step. Then using a calibration stick, the diameter of the tennis ball in the image was set as reference scale. This converts all the image pixels to the dimensions of reality (approximate). After that, the ball is set as the tracking object and its path is traced. The tool traces the object through the series of frames and draws a line through the path travelled. Once the tracking is complete, the axes is aligned parallel to the traced path (required to process the data, which is explained next) and the data, which the tool simultaneously calculates, of time (t, s), x-coordinate (x, m), y-coordinate (y, m), mean velocity (v, m/s) and x-component velocity (vx, m/s) values are exported.

The exported data forms the raw velocity data from the videos. It has to be further processed to derive one value of velocity for each video. The Tracker data, as explained previously, consisted of time (s), x-coordinate values (x, m), y-coordinate values (y, m), calculated velocity (v, m/s), x-component velocity (vx, m/s) and y-component velocity (vy, m/s). In order to explain the process of extraction, it is first important to understand the kind of data that is obtained and the final type of data that is desired. This is explained through the Figure nn.

The graph in the Figure 37 indicates the path traced by the ball in the video. If you imagine a ball at the tip of the line and a background of the video, over series of frames the ball moves in this path. The path that has resulted is a combination of small movements of the ball (due to the waves in the water, the ball does not move in a straight line, when looked at minute timescales) as well as shaking (by person taking the video) of the video. In the present study, the data that is required is the velocity along the horizontal movement of the ball, which is the velocity in the x-direction i.e. vx. This is directly available from the tool, however, it should be noted that the vx velocity includes all the velocity values from the beginning to the end of the path. This includes the velocity values, which have large y-coordinate values. In order to identify the points in the path (i.e. the required stretch of the path where the ball movement is as horizontal with respect to x-axis as possible), the locations of lowest difference in y-axis coordinate values have to be identified.

For example, in the figure above, we can see that, the difference between two consecutive y-coordinate values i.e.

$$(y_2 - y_1) > (y_3 - y_2) \text{ and } (y_3 - y_2) > (y_4 - y_3) \text{ and so on}$$

So larger the difference in y-coordinate values, greater is the vertical movement (or oscillation). Therefore, it is required to identify points with minimum differences between consecutive y-values. In the example $(y_4 - y_3)$ has the least difference. If the computation is carried out for further points, and if 4 such minimum (lowest) difference values are consecutively present, the corresponding 4 values of the x-component velocities were taken into consideration. An average value of these x-component velocities was the velocity value from the crowdsourced data.